

Strategies to Reduce Feed Cost in Small Scale Aquaculture

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Abstract

Feed cost for small scale aquaculture is a major constraint. In a typical small scale aquaculture practice, aquafeed costs contribute around 60-80% of total production cost. Rising aquafeed cost has emerged as a bottleneck for small-scale aquaculture farmers, as they are having limited resources. Adopting appropriate feed management strategies is instrumental in ensuring that feed use is optimized and that the highest economic returns are available to the farmer of small-scale aquaculture.

Introduction

Due to the global expansion of aquaculture over the last six decades, there is an increased demand for processed feed and an increased cost of feed ingredients over the years. In the aquafeed industry, there is high volatility in the supply of major aquafeed ingredients like fish meal, fish oil, Soyabean meal, etc. In addition to these prices of aquafeed is affected by petroleum price and other transportation costs. All these factors finally resulted in the skyrocketing price of aquafeed.

Also, the profitability of aquafarming operations is of paramount importance to the farmer. Adopting appropriate feed management strategies is instrumental in ensuring that feed use is optimized and that the highest economic returns are available to the farmer of small-scale aquaculture (FAO, 2010). Hence there is an urgent need for research towards strategies to reduce the feed cost.

What is small-scale aquaculture?

Small-scale aquaculture (SSA) can be defined as; System involving limited investment in assets, some small investment in operational costs, including large family labour and in which aquaculture us just one of several enterprises or System in which aquaculture is the

principal source of livelihood, in which the operator has invested substantial livelihood assets in terms of time, labour, infrastructure, and capital. (Bondad-Reantaso et al ,2013)

Possible cost-cutting strategies for aqua feed used in small scale aquaculture

1. Maximum Utilisation of natural food chain in aquaculture pond.

- To utilize the natural food chain at maximum, it needs to increase the productivity of the pond by fertilization. For price-cutting points, farmers can use organic manure locally available at a cheap price.
- Natural food contains various types of phytoplankton, zooplanktons, microbes, yeast, and bacteria, which have unique vital ingredients for fish growth and development.
- A thorough understanding of these complex dynamics is central to improving nutrient retention in the farmed species and the culture system, improving feed formulation, reducing feed costs, and improving the efficacy of feed management systems.

2. Changing feeding patterns.

Changing feeding patterns from the usual one can help to reduce feed costs. It includes

➤ **Optimum feeding**

Optimum feeding means giving feed according to fish requirements. For example, during early developments, fish needs more feed (6-8%body weight) than grow out ones (2-3%). So, farmers can reduce feed during the grow-out phase. During the winter season fish metabolic rate is reduced and usually takes less food. Hence farmers can reduce feed to the required amount.

➤ **Mixed feeding schedules**

Mixed feeding schedule means altering feed of 2-3 days of high protein diets with one day of low-quality protein diet without affecting growth rate and yield. It is also useful in the reduction of nitrogenous input to the system that prevents possible eutrophication in the pond. This strategy can also be useful in the reduction of feed cost without affecting the growth of fish and yield.

➤ **Feeding on alternate days.**

By feeding fish on alternate days, fish farmers can effectively cut feed costs in half while dramatically improving the feed conversion ratio (FCR) of the fish crop. This strategy helps to reduce feed cost along with organic loading around net pens and decreases the eutrophication that can occur with intensive marine aquaculture.(Bolivar, Jimenez, and Brown 2006)

It is possible that the improved performance attained by alternate-day feeding is a result of reduced feed waste, either through more complete consumption of or improved nutrient absorption from available feeds. Experimentation to date does suggest that there are limits to the degree that feeding can be reduced without compromising crop value, as a combination of the first two feed reduction strategies proved less profitable than either strategy alone.

3. Use alternative feed ingredients locally available at cheap prices.

While making farm-made feed small-scale farmers can utilize alternative feed ingredients locally available at cheap prices. There are various kinds of alternative feed ingredients like legumes, root crops, cereals and its byproduct, oil bearing seeds and their by-product animal origin.

4. Use of locally produced feed or farm-made feed.

Small scale farmers can use locally produced feed or farm-made feed which is easily accessible and affordable as compared to commercial feed.

5. Improving farm-made fish feed by process of palletization.

The farm-made feed can be improved by the process of palletization. Because palletization helps to

- Prevent leaching of nutrients
- Reduce pollution
- Add palatability
- Reduce FCR
- Reduce feed cost with optimum growth

6. Use of technology and innovation in feeding practice.

Small scale farmers can substantially reduce feed costs for long-term perspectives with a small investment in technology and innovation. Feed waste and feed costs can be minimized by the use of technology like

• Automatic feeder

The automatic feeder has many advantages like It is inexpensive as compared to other methods of feed distribution and the fish feed can be applied to the pond system at suitable times by adjusting the feeder properly. It does not require any sophisticated components or expensive materials and will be reasonably simple to construct and operate.

• Demand feeder

Demand feeders are controlled by the fish themselves according to their appetite. Some species of fish learn very rapidly to use demand feeders but they are usually unsuitable for small fish which are unable to operate them. The fish touch the rod connected to a plug or plate in the bottom of the feed hopper. This plug normally closes the hopper so that feed does not fall out. When moved by the movement of the bait rod, a small quantity of feed is released.

- **Use of Check tray**

A check tray consisted of basically a net with a square or round iron frame with an edge height of not more than 5cms. The feeding tray usually has an area of 0.4-0.6 m². The check tray is used to check the uneaten feed, health, and survival rate of shrimps and also to check the pond bottom condition.

7. Other strategies.

- **Installation of low-cost grinding mill, mixer, and pelletizer.**

The farm-made feed can be upgraded to pelleted feed by small investment on the low-cost grinding mill, mixer, and pelletizer.

- **Installation of the small-scale feed mill.**

Installation of small-scale feed mills can be done as a one-time investment by small-scale farmers to produce pelleted feed in large quantities.

- **Use of Feed formulation software**

Making of a nutritionally balanced feed for fish required a balanced feed formulation for which feed formulation software can be used.

- **Semi-biofloc culture**

The system is based on the use of mixotrophic organisms and the generation of biofloc. This system can be effectively used to reduce FCR and feed costs by efficiently utilizing the feed and animal wastage into nutrient-rich biofloc.

- **Integrated fish farming**

This involves the integration of fish farming with agriculture, horticulture, and livestock culture. The system utilizes the nutrient efficiently and thus requiring less fertilization and feeding.

Conclusion

In developing nations, a small-scale aquaculture is an essential tool for creating food security and income-generating opportunities for the poor. By providing small-scale fish farmers with alternatives to purchasing expensive feeds, it could help vulnerable populations

combat the rising costs of fish feeds and ultimately to build pathways out of poverty for poor fish farmers throughout the world.

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